

A Convenient Synthesis of 1,4-Diaryl-5-imino-3-imidazolin-2-ones. Part-X^ψ

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In continuation of our interest in using α -oxonitriles in heterocyclic synthesis¹ we have recently reported a novel synthesis of 1-phenyl/alkyl-4-aryl-5-imino-3-imidazolin-2-ones² from α -oxonitriles. We report herein the extension of this synthetic strategy to the synthesis of the title compounds (**2**) by heating α -oxonitriles (**1**) with aryl ureas just below the melting point of the latter (Scheme 1). The product **2** arises by derivatisation of the carbonyl group of **1** by NH_2 group of arylurea followed by cyclisation. The structural assignments of compounds **2a-o** are based on their elemental analyses, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data (Table 1).

Ar	R	Ar	R
2a ; C ₆ H ₅	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	2i ; C ₆ H ₅	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄
b ; 4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	j ; 4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄
c ; 4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	k ; 4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄
d ; C ₆ H ₅	3-MeC ₆ H ₄	l ; C ₆ H ₅	4-EtOC ₆ H ₄
e ; 4-ClC ₆ H ₄	3-MeC ₆ H ₄	m ; C ₆ H ₅	4-BrC ₆ H ₄
f ; 4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	3-MeC ₆ H ₄	n ; 4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄
g ; C ₆ H ₅	2-MeC ₆ H ₄	o ; 4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	4-BrC ₆ H ₄
h ; 4-ClC ₆ H ₄	2-MeC ₆ H ₄		

Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **2***

Compd. no.	M.p., °C	Reaction temp., °C/ (Reaction period, h)	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	δ
2a	259–60	165–70 (4)	3306, 1690, 1639	2.48 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.90–7.91 (9H, m, ArH), 8.62 (1H, s, NH)
b	230–31	165–70 (5)	3290, 1680, 1640	2.50 (3H, s, CH ₃), 7.21–8.39 (8H, m, ArH), 8.98 (1H, s, NH)
c	242–43	165–70 (5)	3286, 1685, 1645	–
d	208–10	130–35 (5.5)	3298, 1680, 1650	2.31 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.75–7.91 (9H, m, ArH), 8.61 (1H, s, NH)

Table-1(contd.)

e	238–39	130–35 (6)	3290, 1688, 1640	2.39 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.88–7.84 (8H, m, ArH), 8.66 (1H, s, NH)
f	219–21	130–35 (6)	3286, 1690, 1640	2.37 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.81–7.83 (8H, m, ArH), 8.64 (1H, s, NH)
g	223–24	170–75 (7)	3250, 1680, 1640	2.41 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.69–7.62 (9H, m, ArH), 8.72 (1H, s, NH)
h	228–29	170–75 (7)	3265, 1685, 1640	2.43 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.87–7.91 (8H, m, ArH), 8.81 (1H, s, NH)
i	224–26	155–60 (6)	3236, 1697, 1660	3.39 (3H, s, OCH ₃) 6.72–8.10 (9H, m, ArH), 10.54 (1H, s, NH)
j	214–15	155–60 (6.5)	3220, 1690, 1665	3.42 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.93–8.21 (8H, m, ArH), 10.85 (1H, s, NH)
k	235–36	155–60 (6.5)	3226, 1685, 1660	–
l	230–32	160–65 (6)	3300, 1685, 1637	1.39 (3H, t, J 6 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.03 (2H, q, J 6 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.69–8.21 (9H, m, ArH), 10.72 (1H, s, NH)
m	306–7	180–85 (5)	3298, 1670, 1635	7.12–8.79 (9H, m, ArH), 11.42 (1H, s, NH)
n	266–67	180–85 (6)	3290, 1675, 1640	–
o	255–56	180–85 (7)	3295, 1678, 1638	6.98–8.72 (8H, m, ArH), 11.29 (1H, s, NH)

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses : C, H, N and also Br or Cl if present.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined on a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Jasco FT-IR spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Jeol FX-90Q spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica

^ψPart IX, see Ref. 2.

gel (E. Merck).

α -Oxonitriles³ and arylureas⁴ were prepared by known methods.

1,4-Diaryl-5-imino-3-imidazolin-2-ones (2a-o): A mixture of aroyl cyanide (23 mmol) and aryl urea (20 mmol) was heated on an oil-bath just below the m.p. of the latter for 4–7 h. On cooling, the reaction product solidified, which was triturated with hot water and dried. It was crystallised from ethanol to afford **2** (yields 50–65%).

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